

Development and Evaluation of a Convolutional Neural Network for Accurate Pneumonia Detection from Chest X-Ray Images Using PyTorch

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Abstract

Pneumonia is one of the leading causes of illness and death around the world, especially in people who are most at risk. Catching it early and diagnosing it accurately can make a big difference in how well patients respond to treatment. In this project, we built and tested a convolutional neural network (CNN) to detect pneumonia from chest X-rays. We used a publicly available dataset from Kaggle and trained the model using the PyTorch framework, using standard preprocessing steps. The final model reached a test accuracy of 93%. This work shows how deep learning and AI can play a meaningful role in supporting better and faster medical diagnoses.

*This project was conducted solely for academic purposes and is not intended for clinical application.

1 Introduction

Pneumonia is an inflammatory condition that affects the lungs and it is a significant health concern globally, responsible for a high rate of hospitalization and mortality. Imaging, especially chest X-rays, is a widely used tool used by clinicians to identify pneumonia. However, manual interpretation of these images requires specialized training and can be inaccurate. Methods using advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), particularly deep learning and computer vision have gained traction for their potential to provide rapid, consistent, and accurate diagnostic assistance.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a class of deep learning models suited for image recognition and classification tasks due to their ability to learn spatial features directly from pixel data.

2 Comparative Review of Related Work

We looked at some recent studies that applied convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to pneumonia detection in chest X-ray images.

An et al. [2] developed a deep CNN architecture enhanced with an attention ensemble mechanism, which helps the network focus on clinically relevant regions of the image. Their model achieved a high accuracy of 95.19%. The performance gain can be due to their use of attention layers and model ensembling, both of which helped improve model strength and reduce overfitting.

Saboo et al. [3] took a different approach, using the VCG-19 CNN to classify pediatric chest radiographs. Their model reached an accuracy of 87.9%, supported by a well-balanced dataset and careful tuning of hyperparameters. The use of pretrained networks also played a significant role in achieving this performance.

Our model achieved an accuracy of 93%, which is higher than the 87.9% reported by Saboo et al. [3], but slightly lower than the 96.1% achieved by An et al. [2]. These differences likely stem from the differences in model architecture and training strategies. For example, An et al. used attention mechanisms and an ensemble of models, which can improve the network’s focus on important features and overall strength which helps boost accuracy. On the other hand, [3] experimented with multiple CNN architectures and hyperparameters but reported their best results using a single model without such enhancements, demonstrated by the VGG-19 CNN setup with a dropout of 0.5 and the Adam optimizer which are default setups.

Our approach led to an accuracy between the two: while we didn’t use attention or ensembles, our model design and training process may have allowed it to capture more relevant features than those in Saboo et al.’s work, leading to better performance. At the same time, not incorporating more complex mechanisms like attention or ensembling could explain why our accuracy didn’t quite reach the level of An et al.

Overall, these comparisons show how architectural choices and training methods can affect model performance, and by understanding these differences, we can better suit models to specific needs and resources.

3 Dataset and Preprocessing

The dataset used in this study was obtained from Kaggle [1], containing hundreds of labeled chest X-ray images separated into pneumonia and normal categories. This dataset is an ideal resource due to its size and labeled structure.

Preprocessing was an important step to ensure data consistency and model performance. The images varied in resolution and contrast. It was necessary for standardized resizing and normalization. Using **NumPy**, images were resized to a uniform dimension which was important for an efficient model input while keeping relevant diagnostic details.

Metadata and labels were managed with **Pandas**, which provided structured

data handling for seamless integration into the training pipeline. The **Scikit-learn** library facilitated splitting the dataset into training, validation, and test subsets. Additionally, **Scikit-image** was utilized for image processing tasks, including segmentation techniques that aimed to improve feature extraction by isolating relevant regions of interest within X-ray images.

4 Model Architecture

The CNN architecture was designed from principles using the **PyTorch** framework, enabling flexible experimentation and efficient model training. The network consists of a sequence of convolutional layers, each followed by ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) activations to introduce non-linearity which is essential for learning complex patterns. Max pooling layers followed convolutional blocks to reduce spatial dimensions and computation while preserving important features.

After the convolutional base, fully connected layers combine the extracted features to carry out classification. The final layer employs a softmax activation function, outputting probabilities corresponding to the pneumonia and normal classes.

This architecture was selected to balance depth and complexity which optimizes the model’s ability to generalize from the dataset while mitigating risks of overfitting, particularly given the limitations in dataset size and diversity.

5 Training Methodology

The model was trained over multiple epochs with mini-batches, using batch sizes tweaked to accommodate available computational resources and maintain training stability. The learning rate and other parameters were adjusted to optimize validation accuracy.

6 Results

Initial training led to a baseline accuracy of approximately 68%, reflecting the model’s capacity to learn basic discriminative features. Through the refinement of preprocessing steps, parameter tuning, and extended training, the model achieved a final test accuracy of 93% in the third epoch. This improvement shows the importance of methodical experimentation in deep learning.

The model’s performance demonstrates effective feature learning and the potential applications of CNN-based systems for pneumonia detection. However, further validation with more diverse datasets is necessary to fully establish clinical usage. Figure 1 shows a representative chest X-ray images from the test dataset that the model correctly classified as pneumonia or normal with high confidence.

Figure 1: Sample chest X-ray image classified by the model as Pneumonia with high confidence.

7 Discussion

This project demonstrates the intersection of computer vision and healthcare, showcasing how standard deep learning techniques can help address real-world diagnostic challenges. While the model achieved high accuracy within the dataset, the scope for clinical usage remains limited by dataset size, lack of external validation, and the absence of clinical trials.

Future work should focus on expanding the diversity of the data set to account for the varied demographics of the patients and the imaging modalities. Engagement with healthcare professionals for clinical validation would strengthen the practical relevance of the model in the real world.

8 Conclusion

Through mentorship guided research, this project successfully developed and evaluated a CNN for pneumonia detection from chest X-rays. Using the PyTorch framework and standard deep learning methodologies, the model achieved promising accuracy which is indicative of the technology’s potential to improve medical diagnostics. This project also provided valuable educational experience in applying AI to healthcare challenges.

Acknowledgments

The code used in this study is publicly available at: <https://github.com/aryans42/CNN-PNA-CV>

References

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